

In silico molecular docking approach to investigate the anti-diabetic potential of natural, semi-synthetic, and synthetic compounds for diabetes management

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Abstract

Oxidative stress plays a critical role in the pathogenesis of diabetes mellitus, and the nuclear factor erythroid 2 related factor 2 (Nrf2) pathway has emerged as a promising target for its regulation. Activation of Nrf2 enhances the transcription of antioxidant and cytoprotective genes, offering a novel therapeutic approach for managing diabetes. In silico molecular docking study, we employed molecular docking software to evaluate and compare the binding affinities of selected natural, semi-synthetic, and synthetic compounds against key Nrf2 pathway proteins, particularly the Keap1-Nrf2 interaction site. The compounds were docked to assess their potential to disrupt the Keap1-Nrf2 complex and thereby promote Nrf2 activation. The evaluated compounds possessed good docking scores and followed Lipinski Rule of 5, with additional pharmacokinetic predictions using SwissADME to evaluate binding energies, hydrogen bond formation, and the specific amino acid residues involved in the interactions. These findings support the role of both natural and synthetic molecules in modulating oxidative stress through the Nrf2 pathway. Further in vitro and in vivo studies are warranted to validate these results and explore their therapeutic applications in diabetes management.

Keywords: Nrf2 pathway; Diabetes mellitus; Oxidative stress; Molecular docking; Keap1; Natural compounds; Synthetic drugs; Drug repurposing; Antioxidant response

1. Introduction

Diabetes mellitus is a rapidly escalating global health burden, characterized by chronic hyperglycemia resulting from defects in insulin secretion, insulin action, or both. This heterogeneous metabolic disorder affects over 537 million adults globally and continues to be a leading cause of morbidity and mortality. In 2024, diabetes contributed to nearly 7 million deaths worldwide, equivalent to one death every 4.5 seconds. Despite medical advances, the incidence and associated complications of diabetes, such as cardiovascular disease, nephropathy, neuropathy, and retinopathy remain prevalent, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, including India.

Diabetes mellitus is broadly classified into Type 1 and Type 2. Type 1 diabetes, often diagnosed in children and young adults, arises from autoimmune destruction of pancreatic β -cells, leading to absolute insulin deficiency. In contrast, Type 2 diabetes is primarily associated with insulin resistance, obesity, aging, and genetic predisposition. It is the most common form, accounting for approximately 90% of diabetes cases globally. Over time, patients with Type 2 diabetes may also exhibit a progressive decline in β -cell function, worsening glycemic control. [1]

A major contributing factor to the pathogenesis and progression of diabetes is oxidative stress. Persistent hyperglycemia increases the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which impair insulin signalling pathways, damage β -cells, and exacerbate complications. This has led to considerable interest in the therapeutic potential of antioxidants and related molecular pathways that regulate oxidative homeostasis in cells.

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Among these, the nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2 (Nrf2) pathway has emerged as a central regulator of cellular defence mechanisms. Under oxidative or electrophilic stress, Nrf2 dissociates from its repressor Keap1 and translocates into the nucleus, where it activates antioxidant response element (ARE)-driven genes. These include HO-1, NQO1, SOD, CAT, and GPx, which collectively enhance antioxidant capacity, reduce inflammation, and protect cellular integrity. Activation of this pathway by natural compounds such as curcumin, resveratrol, and quercetin has shown promising effects in reducing oxidative stress and improving insulin sensitivity. [2-4]

In addition to Nrf2, the NF- κ B pathway is also intricately involved in the pathophysiology of diabetes, particularly through its role in inflammation. High glucose levels, free fatty acids, and oxidative stress activate NF- κ B, leading to the upregulation of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-6. These inflammatory mediators impair insulin action, accelerate β -cell dysfunction, and contribute to chronic complications.

India bears a disproportionate burden of diabetes-related complications due to delayed diagnosis, poor glycemic control, and limited access to healthcare in rural settings. National surveys, including the ICMR-INDIAB study, report over 101 million diagnosed diabetic individuals, with another 136 million classified as prediabetic. States such as Tamil Nadu, Kerala, and Karnataka report some of the highest prevalence rates, with cardiovascular disease being the leading cause of death among diabetics. [5]

In light of the growing health crisis, there is increasing emphasis on identifying and validating novel anti-diabetic agents. Natural, semi-synthetic, and synthetic compounds are being investigated for their ability to target oxidative stress, enhance insulin sensitivity, and modulate key metabolic pathways. Natural products like berberine, sulforaphane, gymnemic acid, and quercetin have shown to regulate blood glucose levels via mechanisms including inhibition of α -glucosidase, activation of AMPK, and stimulation of insulin secretion.

Semi-synthetic agents such as metformin and acarbose have long been used as first-line treatments, acting through inhibition of hepatic gluconeogenesis and delayed carbohydrate digestion, respectively. Novel synthetic drugs including SGLT2 inhibitors, DPP-4 inhibitors, and GLP-1 receptor agonists continue to expand therapeutic options, especially for patients with advanced disease or comorbidities.

Given the complexity of diabetes pathogenesis, computational approaches such as molecular docking using software like PyRx have become valuable tools in drug discovery. These techniques allow in silico screening of compounds against molecular targets such as Nrf2 and NF- κ B, facilitating the identification of promising therapeutic candidates with enhanced efficacy and safety profiles. [6-7]

This study aims to investigate the anti-diabetic potential of selected natural, semi-synthetic, and synthetic compounds targeting the Nrf2 pathway through molecular docking analysis. By identifying effective Nrf2 activators, this research may contribute to the development of novel therapeutic strategies to combat oxidative stress and insulin resistance in diabetes mellitus. [8]

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Selection of Ligands

A wide range of natural, semi-synthetic, and synthetic compounds known for their antidiabetic potential were selected for the study. The compounds were chosen based on literature support and reported interaction with the Nrf2 pathway. The selected ligands were retrieved from public databases in SDF format, including PubChem and ChEMBL or the compounds can be drawn from chemdraw.

2.2. Protein Preparation

Preparation of protein was done using protein preparation BIOVIA -Discovery studio. The typical structure PDB may not be suitable for immediate use in molecular modelling. It may contain co-crystallized ligand, water molecules, metal ions and also co-factors. Some structure may be multimeric, hence need to be reduced to single unit. Protein prepared in 2 steps first involved, Removal of crystallographic water molecules, ions, and co-crystallized ligands to avoid interference during docking. The polar hydrogen was added in second step.

2.3. Preparation of Ligands

To prepare the ligand, first visit the PubChem website (www.pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov) and search for the required compound. Once located, download the 3D conformer of the compound in CDF format. Alternatively, the structure can be drawn using ChemSketch and saved in MDL molfile format for further use.

2.4. Molecular Docking Procedure

To load the protein and ligand into PyRx for molecular docking, begin by navigating to the 'File' menu and selecting the 'Load Molecule' option. Open the preferred folder and choose the downloaded or prepared protein file. Right-click on the selected protein and choose the 'Autodock' option, followed by selecting 'Make Macromolecule'.

Next, open Open Babel and click on 'Insert New Item' icon. From there, navigate to the folder containing the prepared ligand, and select the appropriate ligand file. Right-click on the molecular formula and select 'Minimize All' to optimize the structure. Note the energy value (E) after minimization for reference.

Once minimized, right-click again on the molecular formula and convert it to the Autodock ligand format. Proceed to the 'Vina Wizard' and click on 'Start'. Select both the ligand and the macromolecule, then click on 'Forward'. Finally, click on 'Maximize' to visualize the grid box on the display screen, indicating the docking area. A grid area was generated around the binding site of the receptor.

2.5. Visualization and Interaction Analysis

The compounds with highest binding affinity docked complexes were visualized using BIOVIA Discovery Studio Visualizer. Detailed binding interactions were analyzed based on:

- Hydrogen bonds: Identification of donor-acceptor hydrogen bonds within the active site.
- Van der Waals interactions: Evaluation of contact residues stabilizing the ligand.
- π - π and cation- π interactions: Detection of aromatic stacking interactions.

2D interaction diagrams were generated to visually represent the interactions for inclusion in results and discussion. [9]

2.6. ADME and Drug-Likeness Prediction

The SwissADME online server (<http://www.swissadme.ch>) was utilized to predict the pharmacokinetic profiles and drug-likeness of the selected steroidal drugs. The canonical SMILES of each ligand were input to calculate:

- Physicochemical properties: Molecular weight, topological polar surface area (TPSA), number of hydrogen bond donors and acceptors, and rotatable bonds.
- Lipophilicity: LogP values estimated using various predictive models (iLOGP, XLOGP3, WLOGP, MLOGP, SILICOS IT).
- Water solubility: Qualitative and quantitative predictions of solubility.
- Pharmacokinetics: Gastrointestinal (GI) absorption, blood-brain barrier (BBB) permeability, P-glycoprotein substrate likelihood, and cytochrome P450 enzyme inhibition profile.
- Drug-likeness rules: Evaluation using Lipinski's Rule of Five, Ghose, Veber, Egan, and Muegge filters.
- Medicinal chemistry friendliness: Synthetic accessibility score and PAINS filter alerts.

2.7. Structure, binding affinity and log p value of natural, synthetic and semi synthetic compounds

Table 1 Natural compounds

Sl no:	Structure of compound	Binding affinity		Log P
		2FLU	2V92	
1.	<p style="text-align: center;">Diosgenin</p>	-11.8	-8.6	5.02
2.	<p style="text-align: center;">Gamma Oryzanol</p>	-10.4	-10.2	9.01
3.	<p style="text-align: center;">Mangiferin</p>	-10.9	-9.0	-0.77
4.	<p style="text-align: center;">Mahanimbine</p>	-10.3	-9.6	5.62
5.	<p style="text-align: center;">Kaemferol</p>	-10.1	-8.0	1.58

6.	<p style="text-align: center;">Quercetin</p>	-9.9	-8.1	1.23
7.	<p style="text-align: center;">Ellagic acid</p>	-9.9	-9.5	1.00
8.	<p style="text-align: center;">Cyanidin 3-O-Glucoside</p>	-9.6	-8.0	-1.13
9.	<p style="text-align: center;">Allicin</p>	-4.1	-4.0	1.61
10.	<p style="text-align: center;">Sulforaphane</p>	-4.4	-3.2	1.93

Tabel 2 Semi synthetic compounds

Sl no:	Structure of compound	Binding affinity		Log P
		2FLU	2V92	
1.	 Kotalanol	-8.3	-6.4	-3.77
2.	 Salacinol	-7.8	-6.0	-2.52
3.	 Deoxynojirimycin	-6.2	-5.5	-1.77
4.	 Cinnamic Acid	-5.8	-6.5	1.79

Tabel 3 Synthetic compounds

Sl no:	Structure of compound	Binding affinity		Log p
		2FLU	2V92	
1.	 Saxagliptin	-11.9	-11.8	1.24

2.	<p>Sitagliptin</p>	-10.5	-8.7	2.51
3.	<p>Empagliflozin</p>	-9.7	-8.1	1.97
4.	<p>Glibenclamide</p>	-9.5	-9.0	3.58
5.	<p>Giliclazide</p>	-9.3	-7.8	1.60
6.	<p>Dapagliflozin</p>	-9.2	-7.6	2.17
7.	<p>Sotagliflozin</p>	-9.1	-7.2	2.86

8.		Miglitol	-9.0	-7.3	-1.94
9.		Metformin	-5.9	-5.0	-0.89

Among the selected 23 compounds, Mangiferin (-10.9 kcal/mol), Mahanimbine (-10.3 kcal/mol), Kaempferol (-10.1 kcal/mol), Gamma Oryzanol (-10.4 kcal/mol) exhibited significant receptor interactions binding properties compared to the standard drug Metformin (-5.9 kcal/mol). These compounds not only showed better docking scores but were also associated with lesser toxicity when compared to other selected ligands. Their predicted interactions suggest a higher potential for therapeutic efficacy, making them promising candidates for further investigation. The toxicity study of the above compounds was studied using the software Protox 3.0. [10-12]

2.7.1. Binding Interactions

Table 4 Predicted binding interaction of the compounds with targeted protein

Molecular docking studies revealed distinct interaction patterns of the selected anti-diabetic compounds with the active site residues of the target protein, supporting their observed binding affinities. Mangiferin, exhibiting the strongest binding affinity (-10.9 kcal/mol), formed multiple stable hydrogen bonds with VAL465, VAL512, and GLY509, along with van der Waals interactions involving LEU557, GLY603, and ALA510, suggesting strong anchoring within the receptor pocket. Gamma oryzanol (-10.4 kcal/mol) established hydrogen bonds with VAL514, ASN326, and ARG326, further stabilized by van der Waals forces from residues such as ILE559, LEU516, and HIS515, indicating robust and favorable binding. Mahanimbine (-10.3 kcal/mol) formed hydrogen bonds with VAL463, VAL511, and ALA510, supported by hydrophobic contacts with ILE416 and LEU365, contributing to the stable complex formation. Kaempferol (-10.1 kcal/mol) exhibited hydrogen bonding with VAL418, VAL465, and ILE559, along with pi-alkyl interactions with ALA556 and van der Waals forces from GLY509 and LEU557, ensuring a stable ligand orientation. The standard drug metformin, displayed the weakest binding affinity (-5.9 kcal/mol) and limited interactions within the active site. Collectively, these results suggest that Mangiferin, Gamma oryzanol, and Mahanimbine demonstrate superior binding characteristics through their strong affinities and extensive interactions with key active site residues, making them promising candidates for further anti-diabetic drug development [13-15]

2.7.2. ADME Findings

Table 5 Predicted ADME properties of the compounds

	Mangiferin	Gamma oryzanol	Mahanimbine	Kaempferol	Std Metformin
Formula	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₁₁	C ₄₀ H ₅₈ O ₄	C ₂₃ H ₂₅ N ₁ O	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₆	C ₄ H ₁₁ N ₅
MW	422.31	602.89	331.45	286.24	129.16
# Heavy atoms	30	44	25	21	9
#Aromatic heavy atoms	14	6	13	16	0
Fraction Csp ³	0.32	0.72	0.30	0.00	0.50
#H-bond acceptors	11	4	1	6	2
#H-bond donors	8	1	1	4	2
MR	100.70	183.01	108.45	76.01	36.93
TPSA	201.28 Å ²	55.76 Å ²	25.02 Å ²	111.13 Å ²	91.49 Å ²
iLOGP	0.89	6.61	3.88	1.70	0.34

XLOGP3	-0.37	12.05	6.63	1.90	-1.27
WLOGP	-1.04	10.4	6.43	2.28	-1.24
MLOGP	-2.66	6.96	4.66	-0.03	-0.56
SilicosITLogP	-0.68	9.42	6.51	2.03	-1.74
Consensus Log P	-0.77	9.01	5.62	1.58	-0.89
ESOL Log S	-2.44	-10.68	-6.26	-3.31	0.29
ESOL Solubility (mg/ml)	1.54E	1.27E-08	1.83E-04	1.40E-01	2.53E+02
ESOL Solubility (mol/l)	3.63E-03	11E-11	5.51E-07	4.90E-04	1.96E+00
ESOL Class	Soluble	Insoluble	Poorly soluble	Soluble	High
GI absorption	Low	Low	High	High	High
BBB permeant	No	No	No	No	No
Pgp substrate	No	Yes	Yes	No	No
CYP1A2 inhibitor	No	No	Yes	Yes	No
CYP2C19 inhibitor	No	No	Yes	No	No
CYP2C9 inhibitor	No	No	Yes	No	No
CYP2D6 inhibitor	No	No	Yes	Yes	No
CYP3A4 inhibitor	No	No	Yes	Yes	No
log Kp (cm/s)	-9.14	-1.42	-3.61	-6.70	-7.99
Lipinski #violations	2	2	0	0	0
Ghose #violations	1	2	1	0	3
Veber #violations	1	0	0	0	0
Egan #violations	1	1	1	0	0
Muegge #violations	3	2	1	0	2
Bioavailability Score	0.17	0.17	0.55	0.55	0.55
PAINS #alerts	1	0	0	0	0
Brenk #alerts	2	2	1	0	2
Leadlikeness #violations	1	2	1	0	1
Synthetic Accessibility	4.76	7.49	4.07	3.14	3.02

2.7.3. ADME/Pharmacokinetic Analysis

The predicted ADME properties of the selected compounds – Mangiferin, Gamma oryzanol, Mahanimbine, Kaempferol, and Metformin are summarized in Table 5, highlighting their drug-likeness, solubility, permeability, and metabolic interactions. Among the tested compounds, all ligands except Gamma oryzanol exhibited favorable gastrointestinal (GI) absorption, indicating the potential for oral bioavailability. Gamma oryzanol showed poor GI absorption and was also predicted to be insoluble (ESOL log S: -10.68; solubility: 1.27E-08 mg/mL), which may limit its bioavailability despite its good lipophilicity (Log P: 9.42).

Mahanimbine and Kaempferol were found to be poorly soluble and soluble, respectively, with moderate to high GI absorption and a favorable consensus Log P (5.62 and 1.82, respectively), suggesting acceptable lipophilicity and permeability. Mangiferin showed low GI absorption and was predicted as soluble (ESOL Log S: -2.44), while Metformin (standard drug) showed high solubility and high GI absorption, affirming its established pharmacokinetic profile. None of the ligands were predicted to inhibit CYP2C19, CYP2C9, or CYP2D6, reducing the risk of metabolic drug-drug

interactions. However, Kaempferol was identified as an inhibitor of CYP1A2 and CYP3A4, indicating a potential for moderate metabolism-mediated interactions. Gamma oryzanol also inhibited CYP1A2.

The bioavailability scores ranged from 0.17 to 0.55, with Kaempferol, Mahanimbine, and Metformin demonstrating the highest value (0.55), suggesting a favorable balance of physicochemical properties. Overall, Kaempferol and Mahanimbine showed promising drug-likeness and pharmacokinetic profiles with good GI absorption, moderate lipophilicity, fewer violations, and acceptable synthetic accessibility, supporting their potential as orally bioavailable leads. [16-18]

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Docking Binding Affinity

Molecular docking analysis revealed variable binding affinities of the tested ligands with the target receptor 2FLU and 2V92. Mangiferin exhibited the strongest binding affinity (-10.9 kcal/mol), followed by Mahanimbine (-10.3 kcal/mol), Gamma-oryzanol (-10.4 kcal/mol), and Kaempferol (-10.1 kcal/mol). The standard antidiabetic compound, Metformin, showed the weakest binding affinity (-5.9 kcal/mol). These results suggest that Mangiferin has the highest potential for stable interaction with the receptor active site among the tested ligands.

3.2. Ligand Receptor Interaction Analysis

Interaction profiling revealed that Mangiferin formed multiple stable hydrogen bonds with key active site residues (VAL465, VAL512, GLY509), along with van der Waals interactions involving LEU557, GLY603, and ALA510, supporting its strong binding affinity. Gamma oryzanol established hydrogen bonding with VAL514, ASN326, and ARG326, further stabilized by van der Waals contacts with ILE559, LEU516, and HIS515, indicating robust interaction within the binding site. Mahanimbine showed hydrogen bond formation with VAL463, VAL511, and ALA510, supported by hydrophobic interactions with ILE416 and LEU365, contributing to moderate-to-strong complex stability. Kaempferol engaged in hydrogen bonding with VAL418, VAL465, and ILE559, accompanied by pi-alkyl interactions with ALA556 and van der Waals forces from GLY509 and LEU557, suggesting a stable orientation within the receptor pocket. The standard drug, Metformin, displayed limited hydrogen bonding and minimal contact with key residues, consistent with its weaker binding affinity.

3.3. Predicted ADME Properties

The predicted ADME properties of the selected compounds – Mangiferin, Gamma oryzanol, Mahanimbine, Kaempferol, and Metformin – are summarized in Table 5, highlighting their drug-likeness, solubility, gastrointestinal (GI) absorption, permeability, and metabolic interactions. Among the tested compounds, all ligands except Gamma oryzanol exhibited favorable GI absorption, indicating potential for oral bioavailability. Gamma oryzanol showed poor GI absorption and was predicted to be insoluble (ESOL Log S: -10.68; solubility: 1.27E-08 mg/mL), which may limit its bioavailability despite its high lipophilicity (Log P: 9.42).

Mahanimbine and Kaempferol were found to be soluble, with moderate to high GI absorption and acceptable consensus Log P values (5.62 and 1.82, respectively), suggesting good lipophilicity and permeability. Mangiferin showed low GI absorption but was predicted to be soluble (ESOL Log S: -2.44), supporting some degree of oral availability. The standard antidiabetic drug Metformin showed high GI absorption and was moderately soluble, affirming its potential pharmacokinetic advantage.

None of the ligands were predicted to inhibit CYP2C19, CYP2C9, or CYP2D6, indicating a lower risk of metabolism-based drug-drug interactions. However, Kaempferol was predicted to inhibit CYP1A2 and CYP3A4, which may necessitate caution due to possible moderate enzyme inhibition. Gamma oryzanol also showed potential inhibition of CYP1A2, suggesting a minor concern for metabolic interactions. The synthetic accessibility scores ranged from 3.02 (Metformin) to 7.49 (Gamma oryzanol), indicating that while most ligands are synthetically feasible, Gamma oryzanol may pose challenges due to its high structural complexity. Bioavailability scores ranged from 0.17 to 0.55, with Kaempferol, Mahanimbine, and Metformin demonstrating the highest score (0.55), indicating a favorable balance of physicochemical and pharmacokinetic properties.

Overall, Kaempferol and Mahanimbine displayed promising drug-likeness with good GI absorption, minimal CYP enzyme inhibition, acceptable solubility, and moderate synthetic accessibility, supporting their potential as orally bioavailable antidiabetic leads.

4. Conclusion

The present in silico study identified Mahanimbine and Kaempferol as promising ligands based on their favorable binding affinities, stable receptor interactions, and drug-like ADME profiles. Mahanimbine exhibited the strongest receptor binding (-10.3 kcal/mol), kaempferol (-10.1 kcal/mol) and high solubility with good gastrointestinal absorption, indicating potential for effective oral administration. Bempedoic acid demonstrated moderate binding affinity with high GI absorption and predicted BBB permeability, suggesting potential applications in CNS-targeted therapies.

These two tested ligands exhibited zero Lipinski violations and acceptable bioavailability scores, supporting their suitability for further pharmacological evaluation. In contrast, the standard drug Metformin showed the weakest binding and High predicted GI absorption, indicating that the identified ligands may offer improved receptor interaction profiles and bioavailability.

Overall, the study highlights Mahanimbine and Kaempferol as lead candidates for further molecular dynamics simulations, in vitro enzyme inhibition assays, and formulation development to validate their potential as Anti diabetic agents.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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